

Optimal location and sizing of energy storage systems in DC-electrified railway lines using a Coral Reefs Optimization algorithm with Substrate Layers

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Abstract: This paper deals with the problem of finding the optimal location and sizing of Energy Storage Systems in DC-electrified railway lines. These devices increment the use of the regenerated energy produced by the trains in the braking phases, as they store the energy to later provide to the catenary the excess of regenerated energy, that otherwise would be lost in the rheostats. However, these infrastructures require a high initial investment that, in some cases, may question their profitability. We propose a multi-method ensemble meta-heuristic to obtain the optimal solution to the problem, with a high level of accuracy. Specifically, the Coral Reefs Optimization with Substrate Layers (CRO-SL) is proposed, an evolutionary-type approach able to run different search procedures within the same population. We will evaluate the performance of the CRO-SL in the problem, and we will show that it performs better than the best known existing meta-heuristics for this problem.

Keywords: Railway lines; Energy Storage Systems; multi-method ensembles; CRO-SL algorithm; meta-heuristics.

1. Introduction

In the fight against climate change that occurs nowadays, there is a need for urban DC-electrified railway systems (such as tramway or metro systems), to become more energy efficient. Indeed, [1] states that energy efficiency goals are one of the main drivers for the future evolution of transportation systems. Among the possible ways to achieve it, the installation of electrical infrastructure improvements, such as Reversible Substations (RSs) [2–6] or wayside Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) [2,4,7–9], are within the measures with the highest energy saving potentials. These measures increment the use of the regenerated energy produced by the trains in the braking phases, as they give back to the utility grid (in the case of the RSs) or store to later provide to the catenary (in the case of the ESSs) the excess of regenerated energy, that otherwise would be lost in the rheostats. However, these infrastructures require a high initial investment that, in some cases, may question their profitability. Due to this, railway operators must use accurate methodologies to study in detail the impact that the installation of these improvements has on the system's energy efficiency, as well as their associated profitability before taking the final decision on whether or not undertaking the installation. These methodologies must be based on the application of optimization algorithms, which determine the optimum installation in combination with accurate railway simulation models (in charge of assessing the energy saving obtained with the installation of the improvements). The high flexibility and great capacity to successfully deal with the

Citation: Lastname, F.; Lastname, F.; Lastname, F. Title. *Energies* **2021**, *1*, 0. <https://doi.org/>

Received:

Accepted:

Published:

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

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34 computationally intensive and highly non-linear and non-convex problems posed by
35 the railway simulations, makes nature-inspired optimization algorithms a very good
36 choice to tackle the optimization of the installation of infrastructure improvements.
37 Nevertheless, there are few examples in the literature that combine the use of this type of
38 algorithms with the application of railway simulation models. Among them, we can find
39 authors that focus on the optimization of the RSs installation [10–12] or ESSs [13–15].

40 However, all these previous examples use low accurate railway simulation models,
41 especially from the point of view of the traffic modelling. As stated in [16], the traffic
42 model has a great impact when analyzing the receptivity (ability to re-use the regenerated
43 energy) of a line and, in general terms, the efficiency. Thus, an oversimplified traffic
44 model consisting of a single traffic timetable with constant dwell times can lead to
45 significant errors in the computation of the energy saving figures and, consequently,
46 to an incorrect decision making. In order to avoid it, this paper continues the line of
47 research proposed by [16,17] and makes use of very realistic traffic models that allow to
48 generate a large number of representative and realistic scenarios, so that the information
49 provided by the optimization algorithms is accurate enough to make good decisions
50 about the optimum installation of RSs or ESSs.

51 In addition, even in sporadic cases where accurate and realistic models have been
52 used in combination with nature-inspired optimization algorithms, such as in [18], the
53 algorithms employed may have problems of rapid convergence to local optima (where
54 they get trapped, being unable to achieve the global optimum). This can be accentuated
55 in cases of very large and demanding search spaces, as it happens when the granularity
56 of the decisions' variables increases. The higher the granularity of the power and capacity
57 sizes to be installed (this is, the higher amount of possible power and capacity sizes
58 available), the more demanding the search space is. This can be a problem for railway
59 infrastructure administrators, because if the optimization algorithm used cannot deal
60 with the desired level of granularity on the power or capacity sizes, the decisions about
61 the infrastructure improvements can be oversimplified, leading to non-optimal solutions.
62 For this reason, this paper goes a step further from all the previous research in this field
63 and proposes the application of a multi-method ensemble based on an evolutionary-
64 type approach, the Coral-reef Optimization with Substrate Layer (CRO-SL) algorithm.
65 This algorithm is able to outperform the algorithms from previous research when the
66 granularity of the decision variables is increased and, therefore, the search space becomes
67 much more demanding.

68 In the last decades, a large number of meta-heuristics have been developed and
69 applied in many real-world problems [19–21]. According to the No-Free-Lunch theorem,
70 there is not a single algorithm that outperforms the rest in all possible optimization
71 problems. Thus, the process of designing, testing and comparing different methods can
72 be time consuming or even lead to poor performances. To avoid this point, the authors
73 in [22] present many advises when tackling real problems with meta-heuristics. For that
74 matter, in the practice the number of problems that one algorithm can successfully solve
75 is finite, thus, one of the recent research lines consists in hybridizing different existing
76 methods into ensembles [23] in order to reach a better performance than the original
77 algorithms on their own, and to provide a versatile method that can be able to perform
78 well in different problems. There are two main ways to build an ensemble evolutionary
79 method (EEM): mixing parts, also called agents, from different algorithms (low-level
80 multi-method); or mixing entire algorithms into one (high-level multi-method). In
81 general, the agent represents a search method acting over one or more populations,
82 where the individuals compete or cooperate in the optimization task, but an agent
83 may also represent different encodings, parameter configurations or constraints. Many
84 examples of EEM can be found in literature such as: [24], where two variants of the
85 well-known L-SHADE algorithm were alternated over the population, as each one on
86 their own produces stagnation. This ensemble approach was tested in CEC 2014 and
87 CEC 2017 benchmark functions. Also, [25] introduces a memetic algorithm where a Tabu

88 Search process was used as local search and the global search was performed by the
89 Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization algorithm, showing competitive results in large
90 graph colouring problems. In [26] the authors propose a cooperative framework, where
91 Differential Evolution (DE) and Quantum Evolutionary search methods were combined
92 in order to enhance the convergence speed as well as the diversity of the population, for
93 large-scale global optimization problems. In [27] a hybrid multi-objective methodology
94 is proposed, where the leader direction of the Whale Algorithm is set by a competition
95 among two DE crossovers. Finally, more EEMs can be found in the review given in [28].
96 In this case, the CRO-SL is a novel multi-method ensemble evolutionary-based approach,
97 in which different search methods are applied to the individuals of a single population.
98 This algorithm was first proposed in [29], and further described in [30]. It is based on
99 a basic version of the CRO meta-heuristic proposed in [31] and successfully applied
100 to different optimization problems [32,33]. The CRO-SL has been further applied to a
101 large number alternative optimization problems, in different engineering fields [34–37].
102 The main advantage of the CRO-SL is the cooperation of many global and local search
103 processes over the same population, which allows a balance between exploration and
104 exploitation, and avoids stagnation in local optima. Furthermore, this algorithm also
105 encourages diversity in the population, by keeping hollows in the reef (empty positions)
106 for new offspring.

107 The contributions of this paper are twofold:

- 108 • The main contribution of this work is to apply the CRO-SL in a very realistic railway
109 simulation model to determine the optimum installation of ESSs in a railway line,
110 increasing the number of decision variables (therefore, a more demanding search
111 space for the algorithm) when compared to previous works [18].
- 112 • From an algorithmic point of view, a novel cooperative multi-agent ensemble
113 method, the CRO-SL, has been successfully applied to a hard combinatorial opti-
114 mization problem in the field of ESS design for transportation systems.

115 The results obtained are then compared to those provided by the algorithm with best
116 results in a similar problem [18], to show the best performance of the CRO-SL and its
117 great potential when dealing with very demanding search spaces.

118 The remainder of this paper has been structured as follows: next section presents
119 the problem definition, with details on the problem's encoding, fitness function proposed
120 and its calculation using simulation software. Section 3 presents the CRO-SL, its main
121 characteristics and the substrates (search procedures) considered in this paper. Section
122 4 presents the experimental part of the paper, where we have illustrated the good
123 performance of the CRO-SL in two different case of study with an extremely high search
124 space. Section 5 closes the paper by giving some final conclusions and remarks on the
125 research carried out in this work.

126 2. Problem definition

127 2.1. Formulation

128 The optimization proposed in this paper consists of determining the best config-
129 uration of Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) to be installed in a railway line, in terms
130 of:

- 131 • Number of ESSs to be installed.
- 132 • Location of the ESSs to be installed.
- 133 • Power (kW) of each ESS to be installed.
- 134 • Capacity (kWh) of each ESS to be installed.

135 It must be noted that ESSs have been selected instead of RSs because they are more
136 demanding from the point of view of the decision making (the capacity is not a variable
137 of decision in the case of the RSs). However, the application of the proposed optimization
138 to the RSs is straightforward.

For the particular case of this optimization problem, each individual (potential solution to the problem), \mathbf{x} , from the population is represented by a 2D matrix. The rows of the matrix correspond to the features of the installation. Since the infrastructure improvements selected for the optimization are the ESSs, there are two rows: the first one associated with the power and the second one with the capacity. The columns of the matrix correspond to the potential locations where the ESS can be installed. Therefore, the dimension of the matrix that represents each individual i is $[2 \times N]$, and N stands for the number of potential locations where the ESS can be installed. In a visual way, the structure of \mathbf{x} is given by Equation (1).

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{P}_1 & \mathcal{P}_2 & \dots & \mathcal{P}_N \\ \mathcal{C}_1 & \mathcal{C}_2 & \dots & \mathcal{C}_N \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

139 where:

- 140 • \mathcal{P}_n stands for the power feature of \mathbf{x}_i at location n . The values for this variable are
141 discrete, ranging from 0 kW (no ESS installed at position n) to \mathcal{P}^{max} kW (maximum
142 power that can be installed) in steps of \mathcal{S}_p kW. Therefore, each power feature
143 must take one value from the set of $\frac{\mathcal{P}^{max}}{\mathcal{S}_p}$ discrete values available (being \mathcal{P}^{max}) a
144 multiple of \mathcal{S}_p).
- 145 • \mathcal{C}_n stands for the capacity feature of \mathbf{x}_i at location n . The values for this variable
146 are discrete, ranging from 0 kWh (no ESS installed at position n) to \mathcal{C}^{max} kWh
147 (maximum capacity that can be installed) in steps of \mathcal{S}_c kWh. Therefore, each
148 capacity feature must take one value from the set of $\frac{\mathcal{C}^{max}}{\mathcal{S}_c}$ discrete values available
149 (being \mathcal{C}^{max}) a multiple of \mathcal{S}_c).

Although the optimization algorithms will treat each feature (power and capacity) independently, there must be a coherency between the power and capacity values installed at the same location, which means that there must be an element-to-element correspondence between the values from the different rows that share the same column. Specifically, in case of selecting a non-zero value for the power at a certain location, the value of the capacity must also be non-zero and vice versa. The same happens in case of selecting a zero value (no installation) for power or capacity at a certain location. This restriction will be named “constraint of coherency among features”, is formulated in Equation (2) and must be applied in all optimization algorithms used.

$$\mathcal{P}_n = 0 \longleftrightarrow \mathcal{C}_n = 0 \quad (2)$$

150 2.2. Fitness function

151 The optimal solution that the optimization algorithms must find is the one that
152 yields to the highest installation’s Net Present Value (NPV). Therefore, the fitness
153 function for a given individual \mathbf{x} is the NPV associated with its ESSs configuration,
154 given by (3).

$$NPV(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{[E_{\mathcal{R}}^A - E_{\mathcal{E}}^A(\mathbf{x})] \cdot e_{cost}}{[1 + \mathcal{W}_{acc}]^t} - C_0(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3)$$

s.t. $C_0(\mathbf{x}) \leq M_b$

155 where:

- 156 • $E_{\mathcal{R}}^A$ is the annual energy consumption obtained when the infrastructure is not
157 improved. This value is obtained from simulation (the details about the commu-
158 nication between optimization algorithms and railway simulations are given in
159 Section 2.3).

160

- 161 • $E_{\mathcal{E}}^A(\mathbf{x})$ is the annual energy consumption when installing the ESSs configuration
162 associated with \mathbf{x} . This value is also obtained from simulation.
- 163 • e_{cost} is the energy price.
- 164 • $C_0(\mathbf{x})$ is the installation cost of the ESSs configuration determined by \mathbf{x} .
- 165 • \mathcal{W}_{acc} is the Weighted Average Cost of Capital.
- 166 • T is the period to evaluate the investment (in years).
- 167 • M_b is the maximum budget.

168 The reason why the *NPV* has been selected for the fitness function is that it is
169 capable of finding a balance between the energy saving (the main target from the envi-
170 ronmental point of view) and the installations costs (very important in the final decision
171 about installing or not the infrastructure improvements). On the one hand, the positive
172 cash flows of the *NPV* are directly related with the energy saving. Particularly, the
173 energy saving associated with individual \mathbf{x} is obtained from comparing the energy
174 consumption with and without the ESSs installation ($E_{\mathcal{R}}^A - E_{\mathcal{E}}^A(\mathbf{x})$) and it is transformed
175 into economic cash flows by multiplying it by e_{cost} . On the other hand, the installation
176 costs represent the negative cash flows of the *NPV*.

177

178 The investment will be economically profitable if the *NPV* is positive in the period
179 T .

180 2.3. Middleware between optimization algorithms and railway simulations

181 As previously stated, the optimization algorithms need information from the rail-
182 way simulations in order to be able to compute the fitness function. The description of
183 the railway simulator used in this research is out of the scope of this paper, but it must
184 be noted that it thoroughly detailed in [16,17,38], both from the traffic and electrical
185 modelling points of view. The traffic modelling and simulation include: use of different
186 headways for the different time bands (the headway being the time interval between
187 consecutive trains), use of different Automatic Train Operation (ATO) speed profiles,
188 variability in the dwell times of the short-turn and terminal stations, use of realistic
189 dwell times in passenger stations obtained from stochastic models and implementation
190 of a centralized traffic regulation model that automatically manages traffic operation on
191 metro lines. For more details about the traffic models implemented in the simulator, see
192 [16,17].

193 The electrical modelling and simulation are based on the generation and resolution
194 of the electrical scenarios associated with the traffic scenarios given by the traffic model.
195 A time step of 1 second is used. Iterative techniques have been applied to solve the load
196 flow problem associated with each electrical scenario. The iterative technique selected
197 has been the unified-mixed AC-DC Newton-Raphson method. For more details about
198 the electrical modelling and simulation, see [38].

199 The middleware between the optimization algorithms and the railway simulations
200 is depicted in Figure 1 and enumerated below. This process is repeated in a kind of
201 feedback loop, until achieving the optimum solution.

- 202 1. The algorithm gives the characteristics of the ESSs configurations to be tested (in
203 terms of number, location, power and capacity) to the railway simulation module.
204 This information becomes part of the electrical infrastructure data, included within
205 the data required to perform the simulations.
- 206 2. Several traffic scenarios (selected to represent the traffic operation in a realistic way)
207 are simulated with the ESSs configuration provided by the algorithm. The output
208 from the simulations is the energy saving associated to each configuration. This
209 information is, at the same time, the input data for the optimization algorithm.
- 210 3. The value for the fitness function of each configuration is computed from its
211 associated energy saving and installation costs (see Equation (3)). This fitness value
212 provides the information required by the optimization algorithms to update the
213 configurations to be tested by the simulator in the next iteration.

Figure 1. Middleware communicating the railway simulator and the optimization algorithm.

214 3. Methods

215 In this Section the optimization algorithms considered in this work are described.
 216 First, the Coral Reef Optimization (CRO) algorithm, the basic form of the algorithm, is
 217 explained. Then, the multi-method ensemble algorithm defined on top of the CRO, Coral
 218 Reef Optimization with Substrate Layers (CRO-SL) algorithm, as well as search methods
 219 implemented in the substrate layers are detailed. Finally, the Genetic Algorithm (GA)
 220 used for comparison purposes is also described in this section.

221 3.1. The Coral Reef Optimization algorithm for optimization

222 The Coral Reef Optimization Algorithm (CRO) was recently proposed by Salcedo
 223 et al. in [30,31]. This approach is a kind of evolutionary-type algorithm which imitates
 224 the evolution of coral reefs and the different processes occurring in these ecosystems.
 225 Mathematically, the algorithm considers a square model for the reef (Λ) of size $N \times M$.
 226 Each square located in $\Lambda(i, j)$ is a place that can host a coral $\Xi(i, j)$ where i and j are the
 227 coordinates of the square in the reef. Each coral is a representation of a solution to our
 228 optimization problem. Once we have modeled the reef and the corals, the algorithm's
 229 processes are defined using the following steps: After the reef initialization described
 230 above, the phase of reef formation is artificially simulated. This phase consists of κ
 231 iterations: at each of such iterations the corals' reproduction in the reef is emulated
 232 by applying different operators and processes as described in Algorithm 1: a model-
 233 ing of corals' sexual reproduction (broadcast spawning and brooding) and asexual
 234 reproduction.

235 After the reproduction stage, the set of formed larvae (newly produced solutions to
 236 the problem) attempts to find a place on the reef to develop and further reproduce. This
 237 deployment may occur in a free space inside the reef (hole), or in an occupied location
 238 (by fighting against the coral currently settled in that place). If larvae are not successful
 239 in locating a place to settle after a number of attempts, they are considered as predated
 240 by animals in the reef, and so that solution is discarded from the reef. The coral builds a
 241 new reef layer in every iteration. Note that the CRO approach is an evolutionary-type
 242 approach with some characteristics from Simulated Annealing, since the number of

243 holes in the reef allows that poorly fitted solutions are considered, yet allowing the
 244 search in other parts of the search space and not focusing on local optima. This process
 245 of considering poorly fitted solutions is more intense in the first stages of the algorithm.
 246 Figure 2 shows a flowchart of the CRO algorithm's dynamics.

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code for the CRO algorithm

Require: Valid values for the parameters controlling the CRO algorithm

Ensure: A single feasible individual with optimal value of its *fitness*

- 1: Initialize the algorithm
 - 2: **for** each iteration of the simulation **do**
 - 3: Update values of influential variables: Depredation probability, etc.
 - 4: Sexual reproduction processes (broadcast spawning and brooding)
 - 5: Asexual reproduction process
 - 6: Settlement of new corals
 - 7: Depredation process
 - 8: Evaluate the new population in the coral reef
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: Return the best individual (final solution) from the reef
-

Figure 2. Flowchart of the CRO dynamics.

247 3.2. The CRO-SL: a multi-method ensemble evolutionary algorithm

248 The concept of *ensemble* in optimization refers to a combination of algorithms or
 249 parts of them to better deal with optimization problems [39]. The aim of this idea is that
 250 the new strategy can lead to better performance than any single strategy on its own in
 251 the same problem. In [39], the authors present a classification of ensembles attending to
 252 the type of the constituent agents and its implementation: when the agents are different
 253 types of search strategies, operators or processes etc., it is classified as a *low-level ensemble*;
 254 on the other hand, *high-level ensembles* refer to the methods which combine complete
 255 algorithms to select the best approach for a given problem.

256 The CRO-SL approach is a recently proposed low-level multi-method ensemble,
 257 based on the CRO algorithm defined above. Specifically, in the CRO-SL, a set of "sub-
 258 strates" are defined in the CRO reef [40]. At each substrate, a different search operator

259 is applied to the corals for the formation of the offspring. Likewise, the CRO-SL intro-
 260 duces novel forms to maintain the diversity of the reef and promotes the cooperation of
 261 different search operators within a single population.

Figure 3. Flowchart of the CRO-SL dynamics.

262 Figure 3 presents a flowchart that describes the main characteristics of the CRO-
 263 SL ensemble. Note that the algorithm’s structure is similar to that of the basic CRO
 264 (see Figure 2), but the reefs structure is different. In this case, the reef is divided into
 265 different “substrates”, each one representing a search procedure. The corals in each
 266 different substrate will be evolved by applying the corresponding search procedure
 267 assigned to that substrate, i.e. Gaussian Mutation, Differential Evolution, Two-points
 268 crossover, etc. This approach can be seen as a multi-method ensemble, where the
 269 different search procedures in each substrate cooperate in order to obtain the best
 270 solution to the optimization problem at hand. See [41] for further details on the proposed
 271 algorithm.

272 The CRO-SL was first introduced in [29], and further developed in [40]. As pre-
 273 viously summarized, the CRO-SL algorithm is a general ensemble approach which
 274 promotes cooperative evolution, where each substrate layer represents different pro-
 275 cesses, in this case, different search space techniques. The CRO-SL has shown previous
 276 considerable results in a large number of hard optimization problems in engineering,
 277 such as Micro-grids design [42,43], antennas design and vibration control in civil struc-
 278 tures [44,45], medical image processing [46] or data clustering [36], among others.

279 3.2.1. Substrate layers defined in the CRO-SL

280 Very different search methods can be defined in the CRO-SL as agents (substrates)
 281 for the ensemble approach. They are usually defined at the practitioner’s discretion. In
 282 previous approaches, it has been shown that combinations of well-known traditional
 283 operators with novel search techniques provide the best set of techniques (substrates)
 284 in the CRO-SL. In this paper, the operators considered to tackle this problem are the
 285 same as used in previous applications of the CRO-SL, such as Harmony Search (HS),
 286 Differential Evolution (DE), classical two-points crossover (2Px), classical multi-points
 287 crossover (MPx) and Gaussian-based mutation (GM).

- 288 1. HS: it is a metaheuristic method based on stochastic optimization [47]. It imitates
 289 the process found in music improvisation which searches for better harmony. There
 290 are two parameters that determine the way in which new larvae are generated:
 291 i) Harmony Memory Considering Rate (HMCR), which ranges from 0 to 1. If a
 292 uniformly spawned value is above the value of HMCR, then the encoded parameter
 293 value is uniformly drawn from the values in the coral, ii) Pitch Adjusting Rate
 294 (PAR) which ranges from 0 to 1, which sets the probability of choosing a neighbour
 295 value of the current larva.
- 296 2. DE: it is an Evolutionary Algorithm (EA), which has good abilities for global
 297 search [48]. The new larvae can be generated either by the mutation or crossover
 298 process. For a randomly selected encoded parameter, if a uniformly generated
 299 value is above the Crossover Probability (CR) value, which ranges from 0 to 1, the
 300 new value is obtained by $x'_i = x_i^1 + F(x_i^2 - x_i^3)$, in which F is the evolution factor.
 301 Otherwise, the value is crossed with the randomly selected encoded parameter.
- 302 3. 2Px: the crossover operator is the most used exploration mechanism in genetic
 303 and evolutionary algorithms [49], since its combination with an efficient mutation
 304 process allows achieving a suitable balance between exploration and exploitation.
 305 2Px selects two random parents and exchanges the genetic material in-between two
 306 random points on them. Despite each substrate is linked to a searching process,
 307 when another parent must be picked, the selection is not limited to their substrate,
 308 but it can be chosen from any part of the population instead. The reason is to
 309 contribute to genetic information exchange among substrates, so they can easily
 310 cooperate.
- 311 4. MPx: this search method is a generalisation of the 2Px. In this case, k points are
 312 selected in the parents. In this work, due to the dimensionality of the problem, the
 313 value of k has been chosen to be 3. Thus, a binary vector decides whether the parts
 314 of each parent are exchanged or not for the new offspring generation.
- 315 5. GM: The Gaussian Mutation is a noisy search method based on adding random
 values from the Gaussian distribution to the encoded parameter values, thus
 generating an offspring. The standard deviation σ value in this work is linearly
 decreasing during the run, from $0.2 \cdot (A - B)$ to $0.02 \cdot (A - B)$, where $[B, A]$ is the
 domain search. The Gaussian probability density function is:

$$f_{G(0,\sigma^2)}(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}}.$$

315 With the aim of exploring the search space at the beginning of the optimization pro-
 316 cess and exploiting it at the end, the parameter σ is adapted during the simulation.
 317 Note that we have considered a version of the CRO-SL where the parameters of
 318 the algorithm such as the reef size, probabilities of reproduction, or substrates size
 319 are fixed at the beginning of the algorithm and they are not changed during the
 320 CRO-SL run. A dynamic version of this algorithm is possible, where its parameters
 321 are dynamically updated during the search process.

322 3.3. Genetic Algorithm (GA)

323 As explained in the introduction section, different nature-inspired optimization
 324 algorithms were used in [18], in a similar -but more simplified- problem to determine
 325 the optimal installation of ESSs in railway lines: the Genetic Algorithm (GA), the Particle
 326 Swarm Optimization Algorithm (PSO) and the Fireworks Algorithm (FA). The best
 327 performance among the three optimization algorithms was given by the GA. Particularly,
 328 the rate of convergence of the GA was 100% (achieving the optimum solution in the 20
 329 instances run), while the rate of convergence of the PSO was only 65% (achieving the
 330 optimum solution in 13 of the 20 instances run). Additionally, the GA demonstrated to
 331 be faster than the FA, requiring less iterations to achieve the optimum. Therefore, in this
 332 paper we have used the GA as the algorithm to be compared against the CRO-SL.

333 The main characteristics of the GA proposed by [18] are below. For the sake of clarity,
334 the general nomenclature used in Section 2.1 will be adapted to the usual nomenclature
335 of the GA: the individuals will be referred to as chromosomes, the power features will be
336 referred to as power genes and the capacity features will be referred to as capacity genes.

- 337 • **Selection:** the *tournament selection* has been selected. A pair of chromosomes is
338 randomly selected from the previous iteration's population (or from the initial pop-
339 ulation in case of the first iteration). The fitness of both chromosomes is compared
340 and the chromosome with the highest fitness is chosen for the next generation. The
341 same chromosome can be selected more than once and the procedure is repeated
342 until obtaining a new population with the same size as the previous one.
- 343 • **Crossover:** the one-point crossover mechanism has been selected. In this variant,
344 chromosomes are randomly selected in pairs, as well as a single crossover point
345 for each pair. The part of the chromosome after the crossover point is exchanged
346 between the pair of chromosomes (this exchange includes both power and capacity
347 genes).
- 348 • **Mutation:** each chromosome can modify a maximum number of 2 power and
349 capacity genes (to comply with the constraint of coherency among features, the
350 power and capacity genes mutated must be in the same position, or what is the
351 same, must share the column in the matrix of (1)). The probability for a chromosome
352 to mutate 1 power and capacity gen (randomly selected) is 20% and to mutate 2
353 power and capacity genes (randomly selected too) is 10%. These mutations consist
354 of adding or subtracting S_P or S_C (each possibility with a 50% probability) to,
355 respectively, the power and capacity genes randomly selected for the mutation.

356 4. Experiments and results

357 4.1. Case study characteristics

358 A real Spanish metro line has been used for the case study, but with modifications
359 on the topology to increase the difficulty of the decisions that the optimization algorithms
360 must take to improve the infrastructure. The main characteristics of this topology are
361 depicted by Figure 4. As can be seen, it is a Y-shaped line with short-turn and terminal
362 stations in the branches and a terminal station in the common section. Regarding the
363 passenger stations, there are 12 in the common section, 12 in the longest branch (branch
364 1), and 9 in the shortest branch (branch 2). Regarding the train services, there are four
365 different types: all of them change from down to up direction in the terminal station
366 of the common section and each one changes from up to down direction in one of the
367 short-turn or terminal stations located in the branches (each type of service in a different
368 one).

369 The main electrical characteristics of the case study are given below:

- 370 • **Infrastructure:** 11 traction substations (SSs): 4 SSs of 6.6 MVA in the common
371 section, 4 SSs of 4.4 MVA in the longest branch and 3 SSs of 4.4 MVA in the shortest
372 one. The nominal voltage is 1600 V and the no-load voltage is 1650 V. The total
373 impedance of the active plus return circuit is 26 m Ω /km.
- 374 • **Rolling stock:** Automatic Train Operation guided trains with a maximum motoring
375 power of 5 MW, a maximum regenerating power of 4 MW and an auxiliary con-
376 sumption of 200 kW. They incorporate a regenerative braking system (pneumatic
377 braking is only used when the electrical braking is not able to provide the braking
378 force commanded) and the voltage threshold for the activation of the rheostatic
379 braking is 1800 V.
- 380 • **ESSs storage technology:** electrochemical double-layer capacitors (EDLC) have
381 been chosen since they have an excellent balance between power and energy density.
382 The ESS management control is determined by the control curve described in [18].
383 This control curve tries to maximize the availability of the ESS to store regenerated
384 energy by setting the activation values of the charging and discharging phases very

Figure 4. Case study line's topology.

385 close to the no-load (V_{NL}). In fact, these values are, respectively, $1.01 \times V_{NL}$ and
 386 $0.99 \times V_{NL}$.

387 Regarding the traffic operation, different moments of operation have been consid-
 388 ered:

- 389 • Very peak-hour with large perturbations: it is represented by 200 different traffic
 390 scenarios with 3.5 minute headway. All the traffic scenarios have been generated
 391 with the realistic traffic model for large perturbations of [17].
- 392 • Very peak-hour/peak-hour/off peak-hour/sparse traffic operation with small per-
 393 turbations. Each moment of operation has an associated headway of, respectively,
 394 3.5/5/7/15 minutes and is represented by 200 different traffic scenarios, generated
 395 all of them with the realistic traffic model for small perturbations of [16].

396 It must be noted that each traffic scenario previously mentioned represents the
 397 operation during a long enough period. According to [16], to represent a typical opera-
 398 tion cycle, the time length for each scenario must be approximately the time required
 399 by a train to go from one terminal station to the other. Since trains can give different
 400 types of service for the case study line, the simulation length has been defined as the
 401 time required by the longest service to make its itinerary in one direction (up or down
 402 direction), including the time spent before departing in the other direction. This time
 403 varies from 3700 secs to 6400 secs depending on the headway value.

404 The distribution of the annual hours of operation with each headway and per-
 405 turbation type is depicted in Table 1 (operation is from 6:00 AM to 2:00+1 AM, while
 406 maintenance is from 2:00 AM to 6:00 AM).

407 Additionally, the train load varies depending on the value of the headway: with
 408 3.5 and 5 minute headway (very peak hour and peak hour) the train load is 90% of the
 409 maximum load, with 7 minute headway (off peak-hour) the train load is 50% of the
 410 maximum load and with 15 minute headway (sparse traffic conditions) the train load is
 411 25% of the maximum load.

Table 1: Annual operation hours of the line under study.

	Annual operation hours	Percentage of total
3.5 min with large perturbations	942.5	(12.95% of total)
3.5 min with small perturbations	942.5	(12.95% of total)
5 min with small perturbations	1885.0	(25.90% of total)
7 min with small perturbations	2782.0	(38.20% of total)
15 min with small perturbations	728.0	(10.00% of total)

4.2. Search space

Decision variables for both optimization algorithms are:

- Locations: Every SS location in the line's case study is considered as candidate where an ESS could be installed, therefore $N = 11$.
- Power to be installed at each location: this decision variable can take any value from the set $[0 : \mathcal{S}_P : \mathcal{P}^{max}]$, where the power step is $\mathcal{S}_P = 500$ kW and the maximum power that can be installed is $\mathcal{P}^{max} = 3000$ kW.
- Capacity to be installed in each location: this decision variable can take any value from the set $[0 : \mathcal{S}_C : \mathcal{C}^{max}]$, where the capacity step is $\mathcal{S}_C = 2.5$ kWh and the maximum capacity that can be installed is $\mathcal{C}^{max} = 15$ kWh.

It must be noted that the search space used in this optimization process is far bigger than the search space considered in [18], where the optimum ESSs installation in the same line was determined using three different nature-inspired optimization algorithms: Genetic Algorithm (GA), Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm (PSO) and Fireworks Algorithm (FA). In that paper, the best performance, in terms of effectiveness, speed of convergence and robustness, was given by the GA, and the only decision variables were the locations of the ESSs and the power to be installed. In order to determine the good performance of the CRO, this algorithm was first applied to the original search space used in [18], achieving always the same solution as the one given by the GA (which always performed better than the PSO and FA algorithms).

In the present work, five instances have been run for each optimization algorithm (GA and CRO-SL) in the new -and far more demanding- search space. With the aim to speed up the simulation time and reduce the computational burden associated to the high number of electrical simulations that must be performed during the optimization process (each individual has an associated ESSs configuration to be simulated in each iteration), parallel computing has been used. Therefore, the configurations to be simulated at each iteration have been distributed among a number of workers equivalent to the number of logical processors of the server, whose properties are given below:

- CPU: Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4116, 24 Cores-2100 MHz (48 logical processors).
- RAM: 128 GB.
- Disk: DELL PERC H330 1.65 TB.

The simulation time required to complete a single iteration of any optimization algorithm is, on average, around 60 minutes, so the time required to run a whole instance is around 8 days. Since five instances have been run for both algorithms (CRO-SL and GA), the total simulation time was around 80 days.

Although computation time is high, this is not critical regarding the applicability of the proposal, because optimizing the railway infrastructure is an off-line process (not in real-time) that takes place in the planning phase. Besides, it must be noted that the big responsible for such long computation time is not the algorithm, but the electrical simulations associated with any new configuration of ESSs that must be tested. These electrical simulations are extremely demanding in terms of computation time because they must solve a lot of non-linear load flows.

4.3. Parameterizations of algorithms and objective function

The CRO internal configuration and parameters used in the simulations run are the following:

- Reef size: 200 individuals (corals) which 20% are initially empty places.
- HS substrate: $HMCR = 0.8$, $PAR = 0.2$, $\delta = 0.8$.
- DE substrate: F linearly decreasing during the run from 1 to 0.5.
- GM substrate: σ linearly decreasing during the run from 1 to 0.5.
- 2Px and MPx substrates: $k = 2, 3$ respectively.
- Number of maximum attempts in larvae setting: 3.
- Depredation process: Probability of depredation per iteration is set to 0.1. If depredation succeed, 10% of the weakest corals are removed from the reef.

In turn, the GA's internal configuration and parameters used are the following. Note that the parameters selected are those which yield the best performance in previous research ([18]) (except the population size, which is bigger because the search space is more demanding in this case study):

- Population size: 200 individuals (chromosomes).
- Crossover: One-point crossover.
- Mutation: During the mutation process, only two positions (genes) of each individual can be modified. The probability for a chromosome to randomly mutate 1 position is 20% and to randomly mutate 2 positions is 10%. If mutation takes place at a power gene, the position is modified in $\pm S_p$. If it takes place in a capacity gene, the position is modified in $\pm S_c$.

Finally, the values considered for the fitness function are:

- $e_{cost} = 0.0642 \text{ €/kWh}$. This value has taken into account the energy tolls established by the Spanish Government and the average energy price for Spain in 2018. See [50] for more details about the calculation methodology.
- The installation cost ($C_0(x)$) is calculated with values inspired on [4] (the storage technology chosen for the ESSs are EDLCs).
- $W_{acc} = 2.5\%$ of interest rate.
- $T = 15$ years. This is a fair estimation of the ESSs' life according to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) [51].
- $M_b = 280000 \text{ €}$. This value makes it possible to try a considerable amount of different ESSs combinations that are within the budget limits and, at the same time, it is restrictive enough to unable highly costly configurations. Railway operators must provide this value in a real project.

4.4. Results

4.4.1. Performance comparison between the CRO-SL and GA

Figure 5 shows the fitness evolution for both algorithms with the number of iterations. The first subplot represents each of the five instances run for each optimization algorithm, while the second subplot represents the average.

It can be seen that the GA, although faster than the CRO-SL obtaining a good solution at the beginning, gets trapped in several different local optima. On the contrary, the CRO-SL is slower achieving an initial evolution, but it is always able to escape from the local optima (where the instances of the GA get trapped) at a reasonably constant speed (measured in number of iterations) and evolves its fitness until achieving a shared maximum value, which is very likely to be the global optimum. Therefore, this shows that the CRO-SL outperforms the GA, especially in terms of effectiveness.

4.4.2. Analysis of the solutions

Before analyzing the solutions, the main conclusions obtained from pre-optimization tests to characterize the case-study line will be given. This will help to understand the search space better. In these tests, it was found that the receptivity of the line was

Figure 5. Comparison of the fitness achieved using the GA and the CRO-SL.

505 reasonably high. Indeed, it was found that, from the power-to-be-installed perspective,
 506 the receptivity is almost absolute (which means that practically the whole amount of
 507 regenerated energy is recovered) when the total power installed is greater than or equal
 508 to 3MW. Besides, from the capacity-to-be-installed perspective, small sizes were found
 509 to be more than enough. This is mainly because the control curve applied for the ESSs
 510 tries to discharge them as soon as possible, so that the energy is not accumulated for a
 511 long time in the ESSs and the probability to accept the excess of regenerated energy in
 512 any time without the need of big capacities is high.

513 The analysis of the solutions given by the two algorithms shows several differences
 514 between them. Since the best solution is always provided by the CRO-SL, an initial
 515 detailed analysis is given for this solution. Then, it will be compared with the sub-
 516 optimal solutions provided by the GA.

517 The optimum configuration obtained by the CRO-SL (the same in the five instances
 518 run) is given in Figure 6 and also displayed in Table 2.

519 As can be seen, the total power installed is 3 MW, distributed into ESSs of 500
 520 MW located at positions 1,2,3,4,8 and 11. The fact of not installing more power (until
 521 the maximum theoretical value from the pre-optimization tests of 3 MW) is due to
 522 economic reasons: the marginal benefit, in terms of energy saving, from installing the
 523 additional power does not compensate the cost associated to it. Small power sizes (500
 524 kW) have been selected in order to install a big number of ESSs, six, distributed along
 525 the whole line, so that they can store the energy regenerated at any part of the line.
 526 Particularly, most of the ESSs are installed at the common section (shared by all the types
 527 of service and, therefore, with the highest number of trains). Besides, the ESSs installed
 528 at the common section, especially those closer to the branches, are also able to store the
 529 regeneration that takes place at the beginning of the branches (the whole line is a single
 530 electrical sector and, consequently, electrically connected). Finally, the regeneration that

Figure 6. Optimum installation obtained by the CRO-SL algorithm for all the runs.

Table 2: Best solution found by the CRO-SL. The solution is represented by a pair of columns, where the first one refers to the power size (\mathcal{P} [kW]) and the second to the capacity size (\mathcal{C} [kWh]).

Location	CRO-SL Solution	
	\mathcal{P}	\mathcal{C}
1	500	2.5
2	500	5
3	500	5
4	500	5
5	–	–
6	–	–
7	–	–
8	500	5
9	–	–
10	–	–
11	500	5
Fitness	363.1 [k€]	

531 takes place at the end of the branches is stored by the two ESSs installed at the end
 532 (positions 8 and 11). Regarding the capacity, all the ESSs have a capacity of 5kWh,
 533 the one installed at position no.1, which has a capacity of 2.5 kWh. These values are
 534 also very reasonable since, as found in the pre-optimization tests, the capacities do not
 535 have to be very big, thanks to the ESS control curve used (which maximizes the ESS
 536 capability to store the regenerated energy that otherwise would be lost in the rheostats).
 537 Additionally, the big number of ESSs installed increases the probability to always have
 538 available (at least) one of the ESSs.

539 Regarding the solutions of the GA, Table 3 shows the characteristics of the solutions
 540 achieved in each of the 5 instances run (each solution is represented in two consecutive
 541 columns, where the first column corresponds to the power sizes and the second column
 542 to the capacity sizes).

Table 3: Fitness values obtained for best solutions provided by the GA. Each solution is represented by a pair of columns, where the first refers to the power sizes (\mathcal{P} [kW]) and the second to the capacity sizes (\mathcal{C} [kWh]).

Location	Solution #1		Solution #2		Solution #3		Solution #4		Solution #5	
	\mathcal{P}	\mathcal{C}								
1	500	5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5
2	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	5	500	5	500	2.5
3	500	2.5	500	7.5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5
4	500	5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5
5	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
6	–	–	–	–	–	–	500	2.5	500	7.5
7	–	–	500	7.5	500	12.5	–	–	–	–
8	500	7.5	–	–	–	–	500	2.5	500	2.5
9	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
10	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
11	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5	500	2.5
Fitness	360.2 [k€]		359.6 [k€]		358.5 [k€]		358.3 [k€]		358.1 [k€]	

543 As can be seen, each solution is different to the other, which means that the GA gets
 544 trapped in different local optima. This is largely due to: 1) the big search space (with
 545 respect to the original search space presented in [18]), and 2) the difficulty of the fitness
 546 landscape.

547 Regarding the difficulty of the landscape, firstly it must be noted that the search
 548 space seems to have a lot of different local optima, since different configurations can lead
 549 to similar energy savings. Additionally, it has been observed that the different variables
 550 of decision have different levels of influence on the fitness function, the power sizes and
 551 locations being the main variables of decision, relegating the capacity to a secondary
 552 level (which means that the fitness is less sensitive to most of its variations). This is
 553 largely due to their impact on the installation costs (crucial for the fitness function): in
 554 all the solutions obtained the cost associated with the total power installed is more than
 555 15 times higher than the cost associated with the total capacity installed.

556 This makes the GA to focus on the power size and location selection (which are the
 557 variables with the highest influence on the fitness), being unable to deal properly with
 558 the capacity selection. On the contrary, the CRO-SL is able to carry out a powerful global
 559 search of location and power sizes, but also an excellent treatment of the capacity values
 560 of the ESS. This way, note that the main difference between these algorithms seems to
 561 be the higher ability of the CRO-SL to carry out a good search for all the variables of
 562 decision, without relegating the capacity search of the solution. Indeed, among all the
 563 solutions provided by the GA, the one with the best fitness is very similar to the solution
 564 provided by the CRO-SL: it has the same locations and the same power sizes for each
 565 ESS, and the only difference is on the capacities of the ESSs, which are better selected by
 566 the CRO-SL approach.

567 Regarding the computational performance of the CRO-SL in this problem, Figure 7
 568 (a) shows the number of larvae (potential solutions to the problem) getting into the reef
 569 per substrate, over the iterations. Note that a new individual can enter in the population
 570 at a random place, if its associated fitness value is better than the occupied one, or if the
 571 place is empty. Due to the initial spots in the reef, in the first iterations of the algorithm's
 572 run there is a higher probability to enter, independently of the quality of solutions, so
 573 this number is usually larger at the beginning of the algorithm's run. In Figure 7 (b)
 574 the accumulative ratio of times that each substrate is producing the best larva is shown.

575 It is remarkable that the best larva might not be better than the fittest coral of the reef.
 576 Regarding both figures, it can be pointed out that DE substrate seems to be the best
 577 for search space exploration and exploitation. The contribution of the other substrates
 578 seems to be smaller, but note how all of them include solutions in the reef, specially the
 579 GM substrate, at the end of the algorithm's evolution.

580 To conclude the analysis of results, it has been shown that the GA is faster than
 581 the CRO-SL but it gets trapped in local optima. The CRO-SL finds the best solution
 582 with fitness function 363,1 k€. The solutions provided by the GA are not the optimal
 583 solution found by the CRO-SL, and the difference in the value of fitness goes from 0,81%
 584 to 1,4%. This would have an impact on the profitability of the investment. In addition,
 585 the decision on the location and the sizes of the ESSs would vary depending on the
 586 algorithm applied to solve this decision problem. Thus, the CRO-SL is more effective
 587 finding the optimal solution of the proposed problem.

(a) # of larvae into the reef per substrate.

(b) % of best larvae per substrate.

Figure 7. Number of larvae entering to the reef and percentage of best larva generated per substrate in the CRO-SL; (a) # of larvae into the reef; (b) % of best larvae per substrate.

588 5. Conclusions

589 In this paper we have faced a problem of optimal location and sizing of Energy
 590 Storage Systems (ESS) in DC-electrified railway lines. We have proposed and evaluated

591 the performance of a multi-method ensemble meta-heuristic in this problem, the Coral
592 Reefs Optimization with Substrate Layers (CRO-SL). It is an evolutionary-type multi-
593 method approach able to run different search procedures within the same population.
594 We have adapted the CRO-SL to cope with the problem at hand, by incorporating specific
595 operators, a mix of the most successful search procedures in evolutionary algorithms,
596 such as 2-points or multi-points crossovers, Gaussian mutation, Differential Evolution or
597 Harmony Search. All these approaches are combined into a single population algorithms
598 to carry out an accurate search for the optimal solution to the problem. In fact, the CRO-
599 SL has shown excellent performance in a real case study to determine the location and
600 sizing of ESS in a real Spanish metro line, consistently improving the results obtained by
601 an existing Genetic Algorithm in this problem in all the instances run.

602 **Author Contributions:** Conceptualization, S. Salcedo-Sanz, P. Cucala, D. Roch, S. Jiménez-
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606 supervision, S. Salcedo-Sanz, S. Jiménez-Fernández, P. Cucala, R. Pecharromán. All authors have
607 read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

608 **Acknowledgments:** This research has been partially supported by Comunidad de Madrid,
609 PROMINT-CM project (grant ref: P2018/EMT-4366) and Ministerio de Economía, Industria y
610 Competitividad of Spain (grant ref. TIN2017-85887-C2-2-P).

611 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

612 Appendix A

613 Appendix A.1

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